

Re-visioning The Past: Inception of Photography in Princely Cooch Behar*

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Abstract

A considerable amount of research is being carried out on the history and development of photography. It is of very recent that historians are also trying to compile history through the evidences furnished by photographs. There are a number of works which consist of the annals of photography in India and a few on Bengal also. But, the developmental history of photography in the former Princely States of India seems a subject yet to be explored. The present article is an effort to showcase the history of inception of photography in Cooch Behar, once a Princely State under the Bengal Presidency. An attempt has also been made to evaluate the importance of photographs as components for compiling the history of Cooch Behar.

Key Words: Pre-photography, Photography, Photographs, Photographers.

Review of Literature:

The History of Photography in Cooch Behar State as a subject has never been discussed separately in particular. Therefore, the references cited in this article have been mostly collected from discrete sources. Pertinent issues of *The Annual Administration Report Of The Cooch Behar State* and *The Cooch Behar Gazette* has been consulted. The only books where there is a direct mention of photography and photographers in Cooch Behar are *Amar Shat Bachharer Okalati [1905-1965]*, (1965 C.E.), by Ambika Charan Roy and *Chabi Tola: Bangalir Photographi-Charcha*, (1988 C.E.), by Siddhartha Ghosh. The latter mentioned work particularly, has been carefully taken into account. The negatives including glass plates and photographs either

*The title is an inspiration from Malavika Karlekar's work *Re-visioning the Past: Early Photography in Bengal 1875-1915*, Oxford University Press, 2005.

in a hard or digitised form in collection of the present author has been thoroughly examined for the identity of their photographers, owners, type of print and paper, studios, monograms etc. Information has also been accumulated through Interviews and Questionnaires. In spite of these sources, which are primary, necessary Books, issues of some Journals, Magazines, Periodicals etc. and relevant Websites has also been consulted.

Introduction

Imbalance of light disfigures a photograph; excessive light causes it to burn while inadequate light shadows the details. Similar is the effect of light on history, excessive light popularises a historical aspect to such an extent, that it becomes a living history, on the other hand its' scarcity propagates the compilation of facts and figures originating from the actual events and ubiquitous myths. The present article which efforts to picturise the saga of photography in the Princely State of Cooch Behar¹ falls under such a category. In addition, it also attempts to offer a glimpse of history through history's very own illustrations.

Pre-photographic era in Cooch Behar

Generally, painting and sketches because of their subjective analogy to photography were once thought upon and still considered to be a progenitor of photography. These are the forms of art which also shaped the subject of photography to some extent. Thus, it will be interesting to travel through time and have a glimpse at the conception and diversity of art prevalent in Cooch Behar before photography had made its place. Usually, painting and sketches, though expensive particularly the former one compared to photography occupied its place before photography arrived and gradually attained to popularity. Even after the invention of photography, those who were able to bear the expenses fancied painting and sketch which were considered as a mark of aristocracy. Cooch Behar was not an exception, especially regarding paintings. But, as we travel back to the nineteenth century specimens become more and more elusive. Except for those miniatures painted on manuscripts, there are no examples as such. It is known that, Maharaja Harendra Narayan (1783-1839 C.E.) of Cooch Behar was very fond of pictures from his infancy. Certain painters used to be seated near him and painted various pictures at his command. He

sometimes even painted with his own hand.ⁱⁱ According to Moonshi Joynath Ghose, the Maharaja was ‘unrivalled’ in the art of drawing and drew pictures of beasts, birds, trees, creepers, flowers etc.ⁱⁱⁱ A few Bengali manuscripts composed by the Maharaja are preserved at the North Bengal State Library Archive, at least two of them possess brilliant artwork on their *patas* (cover boards).^{iv} The conjecture can be made that these were painted by the Maharaja himself, but, absence of any signature makes it much difficult to corroborate. Of these two manuscripts, on the boards of *Upakatha* (Ms. No. 6), a conversation between the *Raja* and a minister, a Royal marriage ceremony, a hunting scene featuring the prince and the minister’s son, the prince *Anangamohan* and his newly married bride *Swapnabati* riding together on the same horse etc. can be noticed.^v [Figure-1] An illustrated Persian manuscript, the *Forsul Fawaid*, composed (translated from *Shalihotra*’s work?) by some Yasin Khan, son of Daud Khan Afgan Madhubir featuring varieties of horses, their different diseases and treatment (*Ghora-nidana*?) is preserved at the State Library. It was copied by Sheik Amanulla and Sheik Helaluddin on the year 1235 B.S., corresponding with 1828-1829 C.E., i.e., the reign of Maharaja Harendra Narayan. The manuscript was owned by some Hayat Khan Saowar. It was copied on foolscap paper and is bound like that of an exercise book. The most interesting part about this manuscript is it has at least 160 colourful illustrations of horses.^{vi} It is probable that the scribes painted the images themselves. Ghose mentions about Maharaja Harendra Narayan that ‘None could equal him in horsemanship or the riding of elephants’.^{vii} Thus, an inference that the *Forsul Fawaid* manuscript was copied on the interest of the Maharaja or at least it formed a part of his collection is not unlikely. It is interesting to note that, these equine races are depicted on other manuscripts also, suggesting their importance and popularity in the region.^{viii}

There are some other manuscripts also which are of considerable artistry.^{ix} One of such a manuscript is the *Harabhakti-Taranga*, written by Durgadas in one volume. At the end of this work an account of the installation of Maharaja Shivendra Narayan (1839 C.E.) is given. The cover of this manuscript has pictures painted in colours. There are coloured portraits of *Mahadeva*, *Haria Mandal*, *Hira* and *Jira Devi*, all are but God and characters related to the Cooch Behar dynasty, as well of the young boys *Bisu* (latter on Maharaja Viswa Singha) and *Sisu* (founder of the Raikat dynasty), Maharajas Nara Narayan, Dharendra Narayan, Harendra Narayan and Shivendra Narayan. Names were put down under the pictures to identify the portraits. Since, coloured portraits of Harendra Narayan and Shivendra Narayan were at that time being preserved at the State Library, Cooch Behar, Khan Chowdhuri Amanatulla Ahmed (1936 C.E.) affirmed the similarity of the picture of Harendra Narayan depicted on the cover with that of the portrait. He

also remarked that the portrait of Shivendra Narayan apparently showed no such similarity, while the others appeared to be drawn from imagination.^x The portrait of Harendra Narayan was published on the *Paricharika (Naba Paryaya)* magazine edited by Nirupama Devi in 1324 B.S. (1917 C.E.)^{xi} and reproduced in a collection of songs written by the Maharaja entitled *Geetavali*, edited by Sarat Chandra Ghoshal in 1327 B.S. corresponding with 1920-1921 C.E.^{xii} [Fig.-2] The same appears to have been redrawn by the Universal Art Gallery, Calcutta (now Kolkata). However, the present whereabouts of the original portrait is not certain.^{xiii} The identity of artists of both the portraits once preserved at the State Library remains equally undetermined. A miniature painting of Dewan Ram Chandra Lahiri,^{xiv} who held the Dewanship of Cooch Behar State from 1826/27-1840 C.E. (?), i.e., during the Maharajas Harendra and Shivendra Narayan (1839-1847 C.E.) is known.^{xv} The type of *Poshak* or dress which Ram Chandra is wearing has semblance with the *Poshaks* as seen in some of the famed portraits and photographs of one of the great poet and patron of arts of the nineteenth century, Abul Mansoor Mirza Muhammad Wajid Ali Shah (30th July, 1822 C.E.-1st September, 1887 C.E.), the Nawab of Awadh, suggesting the trend or fashion of aristocrats of the said century. [Fig.-3]

Beside paintings, sketches are found from the early nineteenth century. The earlier sketches were made mostly by Europeans. Dr. Francis Buchanan Hamilton visited the old ruins of *Kamatapur* located within Cooch Behar in c.1808-1809. His account is accompanied by some sketches of stone idols from *Kamatapur*^{xvi} as well as of the Temple of *Jalpeshwar Shiva*, an idol of Lord *Vasudeva* or *Vishnu*, *Ramurgor* (fort), Sugar Mill etc. all located on adjacent areas and historically connected with Cooch Behar.^{xvii} Sketches were also published on the *The Illustrated London News*, but they are indirectly related to Cooch Behar, i.e., the sketches of the second Bhutan war (1864-1865 C.E.) in which Cooch Behar was also involved. There are sketches of Jalpaiguri, Dalimkote (present day Kalimpong), Bala Pass, Dewangiri; sketches of an armed villager, soldiers, weapons etc.^{xviii}

These pictures, especially the paintings portray the components of images either prepared in this area or related to the same. However, it is not always wise to interpret the subject or composition of art in this perspective since, the composition of photographs alike hand-painted or hand-drawn images are versatile and fortuitous. But, as a reminder, the view of Jacob Bronowski that *'the tools of the past are made to in modern times'*^{xix} is undoubtedly felicitous here as well. The composition of the photographs discussed down the lines shall further elaborate that though the brush and pencil evolved into the camera, keeping aside the advantages and disadvantages of the earlier tools and

camera, the components remained almost the same. It is worthy of note that, while defining the composition of photographs Simon Ringsmuth wrote — ‘*Good composition not only takes time and lots of practice, but studying the works of other photographers along with painters and illustrators who have been creating art hundreds of years before photography even existed.*’^{xx} On the ensuing discourse it will be noticed that many of the subjects or compositions of paintings and sketches knowingly or unknowingly has been transformed into photographs.

In search of a connection — Photography, Maharaja Narendra Narayan, Raja Rajendralal Mitra and the Photographic Society of Bengal

The Ruler of Cooch Behar to reign entirely in the photographic era was Maharaja Narendra Narayan (1847-1863 C.E.). He was sent to Krishna Nagar for his studies and placed in the College there on 4th July, 1853 C.E.^{xxi} Having spent almost four years over there, he entered the Court of Wards Institution at Calcutta on or after August-September, 1857 C.E. (*Bhadra*, 1264 B.S.). Alike his grandfather, Maharaja Harendra Narayan, he harboured special interest in painting from his infancy and within a short span of time he learned to paint well.^{xxii} At the Wards Institution, the minor Maharaja was under the guardianship of the polymath and one of the pioneers of Bengal Renaissance, Babu Rajendralal Mitra (later Raja). The Maharaja remained under his guardianship till 1859 C.E., when he attained his majority at the age of eighteen.^{xxiii} There are no records as such to show that Maharaja Narendra Narayan ever learned or practiced photography. But if we undergo the circumstances which could have inspired him to learn, we can better understand the opportunities he had and the links which could have been established through his interest. For this we have to take a sneak peek on the life of his guardian Rajendralal and Rajendralal’s association with the Photographic Society as well as the Asiatic Society of Bengal. Rajendralal was a member of the Executive-Committee, of the ‘Photographic Society of Bengal’ since its establishment on 2nd January 1856 C.E. He served as the Honorary Secretary and Treasurer of the Society in the first year. In the second year, Rajendralal performed the duties of a Treasurer only, the post of Secretary was at first left vacant, later on Priyanath Seth, a distinguished photographer and scion of a wealthy merchant of Calcutta, became the Secretary. Gradually after the establishment of this Society, when the number of its members reached almost a hundred, one third of them were Bengalis and beside Rajendralal and Priyanath, the list included eminent personalities such as Ishwar Chandra Singha, better known as the ‘Chhoto Raja’ of Paikpara, Kanailal De, a famed Chemist and Writer, especially credited for the discovery of chemicals useful in photography and others.^{xxiv} At least five Articles on photography which Rajendralal contributed to the Society

Journal can be traced. Rajendralal was regarded as ‘...one of the best Photographers of his day.’^{xxxv} However, the lecture in cogent support of the ‘Black Act’ delivered by him at the Calcutta Town Hall on the 6th April 1857 C.E. resulted in his expulsion from the Society on 19th August 1857 C.E.^{xxxvi} The very year on which the young Maharaja of Cooch Behar came to Calcutta. From the inception of the Photographic Society of Bengal, its meetings were held at the Asiatic Society, Calcutta. On 16th September, 1857 C.E., it was decided in assembly to shift the meetings of the Photographic Society to the Civil Engineering College. Siddhartha Ghosh inferred that, perhaps this transfer was an indication that though expelled from the Photographic Society, but, the Asiatic Society ‘secured the honour’ of its ‘leading spirit’, Rajendralal Mitra.^{xxxvii} On September, 1857 C.E., the name of the Society was also changed from ‘Photographic Society of Bengal’ to ‘Bengal Photographic Society’. Subsequently, from 1860 C.E. they were transferred to Dalhousie Institute and the Photographic Society once again returned to the Asiatic Society on 1863 C.E.^{xxxviii} Although, expelled from the Photographic Society by unfair means, Rajendralal was intimately associated with the Asiatic Society throughout his entire life.^{xxxix} He served as the Librarian and Assistant Secretary of the Asiatic Society from November 1846 C.E. to 12th February 1856 C.E.,^{xxx} when he resigned from the post and was selected as a Member of the Society on 6th March of the same; he was employed as the Honorary Joint Secretary of the Society on 1857 C.E.^{xxxi} and later on became the first Indian President of the Society in 1885 C.E.^{xxxii} It is interesting to note that, during the Maharaja’s stay at Calcutta, he also became a member of the Asiatic Society and ‘Agricultural Society’ (The Agricultural And Horticultural Society Of India).^{xxxiii} Both, The Agricultural And Horticultural Society Of India and the Photographic Society of Bengal, had links with the Asiatic Society. It can be speculated, that the Maharaja, perhaps joined the Asiatic Society on the influence of his guardian Rajendralal, but, there are no accounts to show that the Maharaja ever became a Member of the Photographic Society of Bengal. Was it the Maharaja's disinterest on the subject of photography or the expulsion of his guardian from the Society or perhaps something else of a reason which kept him aloof from the Photographic Society of Bengal? The question still persists. The Maharaja started from Kolkata, by river for Cooch Behar on July/August (*Shravan*), 1859 C.E. and returned to Cooch Behar on 14th August of the same (corresponding with 30th *Shravan*, 1266 B.S.).^{xxxiv} It is also known that the young Maharaja, had diverse interests, he performed physical exercises,^{xxxv} and even in the young age also gained expertise in music, literature, arts, signology etc.^{xxxvi} He always encouraged the culture of music and painting in his Capital or Cooch Behar Town.^{xxxvii} However, despite the fact that the Maharaja was the student of Rajendralal, who was himself a famed photographer as mentioned already and the young Maharaja’s diverse interests, no possible connection could be established in between

the Maharaja and photography. It is also quite unusual, that paintings of some of his preceding Maharajas, namely his great grandfather, Maharaja Dharendra Narayan (1765-1770 C.E. and 1775-1783 C.E.), (though found in a later manuscript, c.1839),^{xxxviii} grandfather and father, the aforementioned Maharajas Harendra and Shivendra Narayan has been found, but, no painting or photograph of this short-lived Ruler, who passed away on 6th August 1863 C.E.,^{xxxix} is available. However, after Rajendralal was ‘legally’ removed from the Photographic Society through ‘parliamentary trick’, together almost all of the Bengalis and Indians resigned from the Society. In 1861 C.E., out of 157 members of the Society, only 7 (seven) are found to be Indians.^{xi} In the succeeding years, as recorded on the Journal of the Society, on April, 1863 C.E., out of 300 members of the Society, only a few were Indians, — Chhota Mian, Kanailal De, Manokji Rustomji, Maharaja of Burdwan, Pyarimohan Mukherjee (later Raja), Maharaja of Krishna Nagar and Tulashi Dutta. Pyarimohan and the Maharaja of Krishna Nagar were nominated as members on December 1862 C.E. and February 1863 C.E. respectively. In the meeting held on 29th September, 1863 C.E., Kaliprasanna Sinha was elected. In the meetings held on 25th October and 22nd November, 1864 C.E., Lala Kanhaiyalal and Abdul Rahaman of Rowalpindi were elected as Members. On 1866 C.E., the Maharaja of Jaipur became a life member of the Society and some Munshi Shionarayan from Agra joined the Society as member.^{xli} From the list it can easily be understood, that Bengali and Indian Royalty, mostly started to enter the Society from 1862 C.E., almost after two years Narendra Narayan left Calcutta. Years later, on the long persisting request of Rajendralal’s friend, A. Grote and on request of the High Court Judge, John Budd Phear, Rajendralal returned to the Photographic Society on 1868 C.E.^{xlii} It was almost 6 (six) years then his student the Maharaja had passed away. An interrogation perhaps is not inapposite, did Rajendralal ever took any photograph(s) of his student(s)? Unfortunately, this question equally remains unanswered, since, till date none of the photographs taken by Rajendralal seems to be available.

Ingress into the photographic era

Generally, it is accepted that the first photograph produced in a camera was taken in c.1826/1827 by Joseph Nicéphore Niépce.^{xliii} The process invented by him was known as ‘Heliography’, involving the production of *permanent* pictures by the influence of sun rays.^{xliv} Louis-Jacques-Mandé Daguerre is credited as the inventor of the first practical photographic process. The result of his invention came to be called the Daguerreotype,^{xlv} which was patented by him in 1839 C.E.; every ‘...daguerreotype, as it was called, was unique; it was not possible to make multiple

copies'.^{xlvi} But, the onset of modern photography, evolved from the experiments of William Henry Fox Talbot, involving the production of a negative from which multiple positives could be obtained. This process was patented by Talbot in 1841 C.E., naming it as the 'Calotype'. It was also known as the 'Tablotype'. The Calotype process was time consuming.^{xlvii} The invention of the Collodian process or wet-plate process by Frederic Scott Archer in 1851 C.E.^{xlviii} proved to be a quantum leap. It was through this process instantaneous photography was effectively made possible. Moreover, the glass negatives of this process were more 'finely detailed' compared to that of the Calotype negatives.^{xlix} In spite of the technical improvements that the Collodion process offered, owing to the heavy materials which had to be carried with the photographer during this process, there were photographers in India who still preferred the slower yet 'less cumbersome' Calotype process.^l It is intriguing that, as late as 1868 C.E., F.W. Baker of Calcutta was also being listed as a 'Daguerreo-typist' by Thacker's Post Office Directory.^{li} Our period of photography takes its rise from this era. After the introduction of photography in India on the c.1840s,^{lii} the State of Cooch Behar ensued to the same at least twenty years later.

The first known specimen and its contentious history

Photography was introduced in India entirely as an exotic form of art. The earliest photograph known till date which was taken in Cooch Behar was not an exception. It can be speculated from this specimen and also those which follows that the art of photography was introduced by Europeans in Cooch Behar as well. From the historical records it can be gleaned that the State came in more close relationship with the British Government during the minority of Maharaja Nripendra Narayan,^{liii} when Colonel John Colpoys Haughton (later made C.S.I.) under orders of the Government assumed charge of the State as Commissioner in charge of administration on 8th March, 1864 C.E.^{liv} The image under discussion is from this period, i.e., the c.1860s; it was published at *The Illustrated London News*, on March 1866 C.E. [Fig.-4] We have an engraved block print of the photograph, but the whereabouts of the original specimen is not known. The image captioned as the — '*PALACE OF THE RAJAH, COOCH BEHAR*' was taken by Dr. G.M. Govan.^{lv} The information provided under the photograph reads as — '*The view of his (the Maharaja of Cooch Behar) newly-built palace which we have engraved is from a photograph by Dr. G. M. Govan. At the time it was taken the edifice was scarcely finished, and its aspect was marred in some degree by the unsightly structures, of a temporary character, which still remained beside it, as well as by the roughness of the ground in front.*'^{lvi} The brief description about the Maharaja runs as — '*The present Rajah, who has been educated in one of the colleges maintained*

by the Government of Bengal, has acquired, like many other natives of the highest rank in India, a considerable share of European knowledge and mental culture.^{lvii} Though the year of publication of the photograph corresponds with the reign of Maharaja Nripendra Narayan (1863-1911 C.E.), but, description concedes that the 'Rajah' referred to here is his father, Maharaja Narendra Narayan. Nripendra, born on 4th October, 1862 C.E. was only nearly three years and five months of age when this image was published and he attended the College at least six years further after. As mentioned earlier Narendra passed away on 1863 C.E., almost three years before the publication of this photograph. However, possibly this print is the only surviving image of the old palace and its caption invites considerable criticism. In the Cooch Behar chronicles nor there are any evidences to show that Maharaja Narendra Narayan ever built a palace, neither there are any mention of the construction of a new palace which took place during the early minority of his son. From the image it can easily be assumed that the architectural style of the edifice represents the utilitarian tradition of building practiced by the early engineers of East India Company. Though, the period under discussion extends beyond August, 1858 C.E., after the great revolt has occurred and the control of the British Government in India was transferred by the British Parliament from the East India Company to the reigning British monarch Queen Victoria. From the documentary evidences available, it can be confirmed that a European architect was involved in the construction of a house commissioned by Maharaja Harendra Narayan in Cooch Behar as early as in 283-284 *Rajashaka*, corresponding with 1199-1200 B.S. and 1792-1794 C.E.^{lviii} However, the only palace which was built at least somewhat near the period being discussed was, when Maharaja Harendra Narayan shifted back his Capital from Dhaliyabari to Cooch Behar in the beginning of 1235 B.S. or 1828 C.E..^{lix} The next Ruler Maharaja Shivendra Narayan thoroughly repaired this palace which had fallen in a dilapidated state owing to the absence of his father who went to Benares prior to his succession on the throne. The Maharaja also added some new apartments both inside and outside of the palace. Thereby, the palace became more beautiful than before.^{lx} After his demise his adopted son, Maharaja Narendra Narayan became king. Narendra's biographer, Shashi Bhushan Haldar clearly wrote that several times the Narendra made plans to bring an engineer for the construction of a palace, but, his plans were never truly executed.^{lxi} During the minority of Maharaja Nripendra Narayan, when the British Government took charge of the State in 1864 C.E., there were only four *pucca* buildings at the palace, which were very unsightly and in a ruinous condition.^{lxii} Colonel J. C. Haughton, Commissioner of the State, declared in an open durbar that in the way he has increased the income of the Maharaja and still looks forward to it, he will not hoard all that wealth in the Royal Treasury like that of a miser, but, spend them accordingly on works of public utility and that he also intends to build a suitable palace for the Maharaja.^{lxiii} But,

during 'the Bhutan campaign (1864-1865 C.E.) the only branch of Public Works which received much attention was the roads, and nothing was done in the shape of erecting buildings.'^{lxiv} The condition of the palace can be understood from a comment made by H. Beveridge, C.S., the first Deputy Commissioner of Cooch Behar. Beveridge in 1866 C.E. recorded that the house in which the Maharaja lived was damp and he was removed to an upper storied building in the palace (compound) called the 'High Court Dalan' where he was residing at the time of Report.^{lxv} The only construction work appears to be recorded at this period undertaken at the palace was the erection of a *pucca* wall around the old palace. This was initiated on 1865-1866 C.E., it took a long time to complete and was finished in 1872 C.E.,^{lxvi} very little was done to the palace up to the close of this year, beyond repairing the buildings therein.^{lxvii} It was in 1875 C.E., as appears from the resolution of Sir Richard Temple, then Lieutenant-Governor of Bengal dated July 6th, that attention of the Bengal Government was drawn towards the necessity of erecting a suitable palace for the Maharaja.^{lxviii} On the following year (1876 C.E.) the account of Captain Thomas Herbert Lewin on the State was published, where he presented a brief description of the old palace —

The town consists of a congeries of mat huts, surrounding the brick mansion which is by courtesy called the palace of the Kuch Behar Rajas.

...It covers the front of a walled quadrangle, in which are erected the mat huts which constitute the real dwelling-place of the family. The brick frontage contains but a few rooms, and these are used chiefly for ceremonial purposes...It is in contemplation to erect a more suitable residence for the Raja; and also to build good law courts, and to provide accommodation for the State schools, which are at present housed in the common mat huts which characterize the District.^{lxix}

The photograph under discussion evinces the presence of the brick frontage, with the two double-storied buildings on the front and rear side of the image, though the space in between them on the left hand side is not clearly visible, but a single-storied structure can easily be noticed on the left almost adjacent to the front building. The front building had a portico, in front of which there must have been some approach road which ran parallel with the building. On the right hand side of the photograph there must have been the 'walled quadrangle' which consisted of the dwelling houses of the family and still rearwards, within the flower gardens an edifice which probably was a three storied (?) structure. This assumption is based on the fact that when the old palace was constructed in 1828 C.E., the dimension of this palace was four times the size of the original one and besides the important offices,^{lxx} —

There was a place for his (the Maharaja's) horses, a place for his elephants, a place for his cows, and a place for his camels. In front of the palace gate, there were three companies of sepoy on guard under the command of the Resaldar Jagarnath (Jagannath) Singh. On the south of the inner apartments (of the palace), was a delightful flower-garden, in the midst of which was a pleasure-house (three-storied?) fitted up with chandeliers and lamps and pictures. A gate opening into the palace from outside led to the Gharikhana and Nahabatkhana which had been erected within. That gate, moreover, opened out upon a wide street, at the further end of which there were countless shops and dwellings of trades-people of all castes along either side of the street. These made a beautiful bazar. On the northern side of this road, temples were erected, and the shrines already existing, were brushed up.^{lxxi}

Relevant parts of this description are quite identical with that of Ananda Chandra Ghosh's lecture printed on 1865 C.E. In addition, Ghosh mentions the location of the place reserved for Royal Guards and Commanders to the south of the aforementioned 'wide street' in front of the palace gate.^{lxxii} It is regardless to mention that the temples on the north constituted of the *Shree Shree Madan Mohan Thakur Bari* Complex, marked as 'Tarabari' in an undated map from Maharaja Narendra Narayan's time.^{lxxiii} [Fig.-5] From the same source it appears that the two buildings on the front and rear side of the photograph were probably the 'Baitkhana' ['*Baithak-khana(s)*'] or the reception parlours, the road in front of the portico the emerging (!) 'wide street', the mat huts and semi-pucca^{lxxiv} (thatched roof) house on the extreme right part the *Tarabari* campus and if not over surmised the faintly ornamental, shaded structure in front with an inner wheel at its centre (composed of bamboo?), the famed *Rasa-Chakra* of Cooch Behar.^{lxxv} [See Fig.-6] If the latter is admissible then this photograph published on March, 1866 C.E. was taken before c.1865, while Narendra was still alive (1862 C.E.?) or on c.1865, between the months of November to early December,^{lxxvi} when the *Rasa* festival is held and the *Charka* is constructed. The imaginary building on the right hand side of the image behind the proposed quadrangle must have been the 'pleasure-house' located in the middle of the old flower garden. This house was probably the three-storied building referred to earlier which was constructed in 1792-1794 C.E., since, during the construction of the new palace, Moonshi Joynath Ghose does not mention that the pleasure-house was constructed, but rather decorated.^{lxxvii} Thus, the photograph was taken slightly from the north-west corner of the palace facing south-east. However, the single-storied structure to the left of the

photograph is not prominent on the said map. A decade after the publication of this image, Major Mant in 1876 C.E., was engaged to prepare a design of a new palace.^{lxxviii} This was the first step towards the construction of a new palace after 1828 C.E. Therefore, it can be concluded that the caption printed on the *The Illustrated London News* is contradictory to other contemporary sources, thus, for the most part it is veritably inaccurate. However, the image is of potential importance which offers a glimpse of the old palace, the proposed *Rasa-Chakra* and their purlieu.

Some other early specimens and their probable patrons: If the original prints or even the negatives of the early photographs related to Cooch Behar were available, they would have formed a subject of considerable interest and study. Their carrying substance, i.e., paper, glass etc. and corresponding chemical medium surely would have added further information on the class and type of photographs and photographic processes being practiced in Cooch Behar. In 1871 C.E. Richard Leach Maddox succeeded in his experiments in producing suitable medium using gelatine ('gelatino-bromide process') which eventually resulted in the abolition of the Collodian or Wet Plate Process. Maddox, regarded as the 'father of the Gelatine Dry Plate' died while his process was still on the 'stage of development'. In the following years his invention left to others was improved and simplified.^{lxxix} Our hiatus of another six years following the first published photograph from Cooch Behar brings us to this period and accords us with the second oldest photograph. A study through this second and the succeeding specimens would clearly indicate that the art of photography gained practice through Royal patronage in Cooch Behar, most possibly through British interest or encouragement. The oldest of these assets are those which were taken during the boyhood days of Maharaja Nripendra Narayan. However, present whereabouts of the original negatives and their consecutive prints are uncertain. Chronologically the pioneer among these photographs is the image where the Maharaja is seen with his cousins, namely Kumar Gajendra Narayan Senior and Kumar Gajendra Narayan Junior along with Mr. H. St. John Kneller. It is known from sources that, the Maharaja was sent to study at the Wards' Institution, Benares in 1868 C.E. In need of a change of place, on April, 1872 C.E., from Benares he was sent to Bankipur (Bihar) for pursuing his studies. It was at Bankipur, where Kneller was appointed as the tutor and guardian of the minor Maharaja. Eventually the Maharaja entered the Patna Collegiate School while residing at Bankipur and prosecuted his studies there for about five years.^{lxxx} It can be assumed that the image under discussion was taken sometime in-between c.1872-1874, as it appears from the young age (11-13 years) of the Maharaja, either at Bankipur or Patna. [Fig.-7] There are a few more specimens of the Maharaja's boyhood, but all of them were taken likely after c.1872-1874, i.e., after the first one mentioned above. But their subsequent locations and the name

of farms or photographers are uncertain. The first photograph most probably taken and printed in the form of a postcard by the 'Bourne & Shepherd', which has the name of the farm printed on the left below and featuring the Maharaja in his youth, has been found. This one was taken around c.1878, the year of his marriage with Sunity Devi. To the present knowledge, all of these photographs, besides the postcard, first appeared publicly on a Biography of the late Maharaja composed by Deen Doyal Chaudhuri, an old faithful servant of the Maharaja as well as his boyhood companion, in 1915 C.E.^{lxxxix} Another image printed on this book and the very one on the postcard though different but, from the age of the Maharaja, his clothing and furniture featured in it, it can be ascertained that they were taken on the same period (day?), probably also by Bourne & Shepherd.^{lxxxii} [Fig.-8]

Outside the Royal arena, the oldest of all specimens traced so far is a full length portrait of Baikuntha Chandra Mustofi, the premier Zamindar of Cooch Behar State and a great enthusiast of education. The present photograph appears to be an enlarged version of the original one. It was taken prior to 13th June, 1877 C.E., the year on which Baikuntha Chandra passed away.^{lxxxiii} The implements used in the image are quite simple. Baikuntha Chandra's left hand rests on a chair on the foreground used as a prop, an ornamental drab is seen on the left-hand side of the back ground hanging from the top of a door (or door-like structure?). His personality radiates from his visage and posture expressed on the slightly olive-tinted monochrome. [Fig.-9] It is not clear who took this photograph or where was it taken, according to Baikuntha Chandra's great grandson, Shreesh Chandra Mustofi, this was most possibly captured at the ancestral house of Mustofis at Gobrachhara, Cooch Behar.^{lxxxiv} But, it is unlikely to accept considering the period when camera was elusive at its best. Baikuntha Chandra married thrice, his last two consorts, Jagatmohini and Nagendrabala, were from the Gangopadhyay family of Gobardanga (now at North 24 Pargana District) and the Haldar family of Bhawanipur (Kolkata) respectively.^{lxxxv} It is also said that he visited Kolkata at least twice for his marriage,^{lxxxvi} which appears to be quite natural according to the Hindu custom. Hence, the conjecture can be made that while he was at Kolkata this photograph was taken. However, possibilities of travelling photographers at Cooch Behar are still open to question.

Emergence of photography and photographers within Cooch Behar

Besides, the pioneer image, the photographs described so far are all of c.1870s and most of them were haply taken outside of Cooch Behar. Siddhartha Ghosh observed in his book that it was only

after c.1880-1890s that photographs came into the reach of common people and even while standing at the threshold of twentieth century the camera didn't lose its innovation in the well-to-do Bengali families.^{lxxxvii} Whatever so, it must be added that the camera and the opportunity to use it was at that time still limited mostly to the elite classes. From the c.1880s probably there was a commencement of photography within Cooch Behar. During the grand hunting expeditions of Maharaja Nripendra Narayan which extended from Cooch Behar to the *Dooars* and Assam, photographs were being taken and these came to be published in the book *Thirty-Seven Years Of Big Game Shooting In Cooch Behar, The Duars, And Assam*, written by the Maharaja himself. The narrative of the expeditions begins from 1871 C.E., but, it is only from 1885 C.E. that the images can be directly correlated with the text. The first photograph accompanied with date was most probably taken on the 10th March, 1885 C.E. at the Falimari jungles, Tufanganj, Cooch Behar. It was the image of the first Tiger shot on the year under mention.^{lxxxviii} [Fig.-10] Following this, several other images can be found, such as the first Rhino shoot of 21st February, 1887 C.E., at Guigaon (Assam?); the Tiger shot at Chhota Bhalka jungles, on 22nd February, 1887 C.E.; the 10-foot Tiger, shot on 14th February, 1890 C.E. at Takuamari jungles, Tufanganj etc.^{lxxxix} The remaining photographs for the succeeding years up to those dated till 1907 C.E., with the exception of a few are either with dates or more or less related to the annals of the shoot. It is more plausible that the photographer or photographers who were capturing these moments were professionals and most possibly hired from outside of Cooch Behar. They also formed a part of the Big Game retinue. Lord Frederic Hamilton, who participated in one of the Big Games in 1891 C.E., gives a description of the large retainers of the Shoot, however, he does not mention of any photographer. It is interesting to note that the Census of 1891 C.E. was being taken while Hamilton was at the Camp, thus, he mentions the exact number of persons the Maharaja had brought with him to the Camp. It totalled 473, including *mahouts* and elephant-tenders, grooms, armourers, taxidermists, tailors, shoemakers, a native doctor and a dispenser, and boatmen, an entire Orchestra which comprised of a Viennese conductor and thirty-five members, cooks, bakers and table waiters.^{xc} Is it possible to accept that such a large entourage was devoid of a photographer? Especially when photographs were almost regularly being taken? The guests participating in the games were also carrying the camera. On the 11th March, 1892 C.E., after shooting a large bull buffalo which made a record, near Jamba Mech's village most probably located adjacent to the Forest Reserves, the Maharaja wrote — '*Scheibler and Simpson photographed him when standing at bay.*'^{xc1} albeit, the presence of a photographer in the Shoots is only evinced later on. While hunting a bull Rhino at the Forest Reserves near Mahakalguri, on 6th December, 1895 C.E., the Maharaja remarked — '*I hadn't seen the bull myself, but sent Hatashu with the photographer to measure the length and*

height at shoulder.^{xccii} Guests were also contended with their interest, since, when the shooting party was after a Tiger at Bhalka on the 20th March, 1900 C.E., the Maharaja quoted — ‘Tichborne (Sir Henry Tichborne?) was photographing him, when he gave another roar and came straight for my Elephant.’^{xcciii} Whatsoever, Nripendra’s book on Big Game is replete with images which illustrates the flora, fauna, landscape of the jungles and river side, supplies information on the morphology of animals, physiognomy of ethnic groups inhabiting the forest area and the environs of the Shooting camps and sites.^{xcciv} [Fig.-11]

Very shortly afterwards, from the dated photograph of 1885 C.E. mentioned above, finally there is a mention of emergence of a photographer within the State itself. Kalikadas Dutta (later Rai Bahadur and C.I.E. respectively), the Dewan of Cooch Behar State in his Report of September, 1886 C.E. to the Maharaja, stated that Satish Chandra Mustofi, a subject of the State was practicing photography.^{xccv} But, a single specimen, taken sometime on or after May, c.1887, no other photograph taken by Satish Chandra discovered till date can be earmarked uncontroversially to this period, neither can be claimed to be taken at Cooch Behar. After a span of another decade, Ambika Charan Roy, who had his first lesson of photography from Satish Chandra in 1896 C.E. while he was only fourteen years of age,^{xccvi} started to try his hand with the camera about this time. Ghosh mentions of seeing some of the photographs taken by Ambika Charan while he use to reside at Cooch Behar. These photographs were dated in-between c.1896-1905.^{xccvii}

Conclusion

We have noticed the transformation of the components of paintings and sketches into photographs in Cooch Behar also. Photography was introduced by Europeans in Cooch Behar and probably they were the first enthusiasts of this art in the same. However, it was from the Royal family that photography received initial patronisation. We have failed to establish any connection in between Maharaja Narendra Narayan and photography, but, the quest has led us to more questions than answers on the subject. Through the discussion on the first known engraved block print of the photograph taken at Cooch Behar possibly in between c.1862-1865, we have observed how a single image can furnish information competent enough to deconstruct and reconstruct the known history. Thus, such a photograph can be termed as a ‘codicil of history’, because, for instance they may change our understanding of the prevailing particulars. As we have observed the change in conception in case of the old Cooch Behar Palace, its surroundings and also accumulated new information on the *Rasa-Chakra* as well as the *Rasa Mela* in this article.

There are chances that photography was prevalent in Cooch Behar at least from the 1870s, but, its practice in Cooch Behar can only be traced from the mid-1880s. Thus, photography in Cooch Behar mostly commenced in the post-daguerrean era. From the early specimens available dating back to the boyhood days of Maharaja Nripendra Narayan, it has been possible to construct an image-history with more or less specific chronology. Despite the Royal family of Cooch Behar, we have also found the art of photography gradually gain attention from other elite classes within the Cooch Behar State. Early photographs from Cooch Behar has also put on view their utility in studying different subjects of interest, i.e., not only the conventional history of Cooch Behar, but, provided information on art, architecture, anthropology, landscapes, flora, fauna, ecological interactions, the inter-relationship between distant civilisations and so on. This information does not necessarily always alter our understanding of the history, but, in some cases provides an insight securing further precision and exactitude, supplementing the already available data and diversifying ways of interpretation. Hence, a photograph is of multi-dimensional avail in aggrandising the reliability and information of history. Thus, it shows in brief how photographs can be used as important components of history.

The practice and patronisation of photography and its art within the Royal family of Cooch Behar and beyond demands space for a separate article. But, it is quite clear that photography earned a space among the subjects of Cooch Behar State in between the mid-1880s and early 1890s. Nevertheless, from the following years, as can be reckoned from the specimens discovered so far, definitely photography had made its place in Cooch Behar.

Notes

ⁱ The State of Cooch Behar was founded by Maharaja Viswa Singha on about 1510 C.E.; it became a Feudatory State under the British rule from 1772 C.E. (5th April, 1773 C.E. according to another). It maintained its existence as a separate Princely State till its merger with the dominion of India on the 28th of August 1949 C.E. and ultimately became a District of West Bengal from the 1st January 1950 C.E.

ⁱⁱ Rev. R. Robinson (Transl.), *The Rajopakhyan Or History Of Kooch Behar*, by Moonshi Jadunath Ghose (should be 'Joynath' not 'Jadunath'), Calcutta: Printed By C.B. Lewis, At The Baptist Mission Press, 1874, Part III, The Contemporary Or Mordern Period, Chapter XIII, p. 185.

ⁱⁱⁱ *Ibid.*, Part III, Chapter VIII, p. 155.

^{iv} *Upakatha* (Ms. No. 6) and *Rajaputra-upakhyan* (Ms. No. 11) [— Shashi Bhushan Das Gupta (Ed.), *A Descriptive Catalogue Of Bengali Manuscripts Preserved In The State Library Of Cooch Behar*, Published by: the Superintendent of Press, Cooch Behar State, Printed by: Nripendra Chandra Sen, At the Sabita Press, 18B, Shamacharan De Street, Calcutta, 1948].

^v Sarat Chandra Ghoshal (Ed.), *Maharaj Harendranarayaner Granthavali, Chaturtha Khanda, Upakatha*, Published by: Khan Chowdhuri Amanatulla Ahmed from Cooch Behar Sahitya Sabha, Printed by: Vijay Chandra Bhattacharyya from 'Manasi Press', 77, Hari Ghosh Street, Calcutta, 1336 B.S., Introduction, p. 1 and illustrations on p. 2 of Introduction and p. 32.

Cf. Kalipada Mitra, 'Raja Harendranarayaner Upakatha', *Manasi O Marmabani*, Bhadra Sankhya, 1324 B.S. and Nirupama Devi (Ed.), *Paricharika (Naba Paryaya)*, 2nd Year, 3rd Issue, Printed from: Cooch Behar State Press by Manmatha Nath Chattopadhyaya, Published by: Cooch Behar Sahitya Sabha, Magh, 1324 B.S., p. 147 and 2nd Year, 4th Issue, Falgun, 1324 B.S., p. 217.

^{vi} It appears from a physical verification of the Manuscript that it had the number 32 (P) in the Catalogue (State Library, Cooch Behar). There is also another Urdu Manuscript, *Mansabi Hindi* or *Tasveer*, by some unknown author, it was composed in between c.1707-1712 and written using gold-paint. It has 23 beautiful colour illustrations (— Swapan Kumar Ray, *Kochbihar Rajdarbarer Sahityacharcha*, Published by: Sk. Salauddin from Books Way, 86A, College Street, Kolkata 700 073, ISBN 978-93-80145-55-6, January, 2011, p. 292).

^{vii} Rev. R. Robinson, *loc. cit.*

^{viii} While writing about the history of internal conditions within *Kamarupa*, an ancient kingdom of which a portion of the Cooch Behar region once formed a part, Khan Chowdhuri Amanatulla Ahmed wrote, — '*The well-bred horses of the country, alluded to by the Mahomedan historians, originated from Bhutan or Tibet*'; Ahmed also mentioned about a manuscript, the *Ghora-nidana*, substantially similar to the *Forsul Fawaid* which was published by the *Kamarupa Anusandhana Samiti*. [— Sarat Chandra Ghoshal (Transl.), *A History Of Cooch Behar (From The Earliest Times To The End Of The Eighteenth Century A.D.)*, Published Under Authority, Printed At The State Press Cooch Behar, 1942, p. 69]. [See — Tarini Charan Bhattacharjee (Ed.), *Ghora Nidan*, Published Under The Orders Of The Government Of Assam, Shillong: Printed and published by the Superintendent, Assam Government Press, 1932].

Irrespective of the variety of horses depicted on the manuscripts, i.e., they were Bhutanese or Tibetan or not, these famed Bhutanese horses also known as *Tangan* horses were brought for sale in Cooch Behar even up to 1947 C.E. [— *The Cooch Behar Gazette*, Part II, Notices, Thursday, January 2, 1947, 17th Poush, 1353 B.S., 437 *Rajashaka*, p. 1 ('*Chyangadabandha Mela*')].

^{ix} The author had the privilege to visit and perform research at the Archives several times; he had seen and investigated some of the manuscripts, especially those preserved at the North Bengal State Library Archive (NBSLA), but not all of them individually. The following list of illustrated manuscripts has been prepared from their respective catalogues: — Manuscripts preserved at the North Bengal State Library, — Bengali Manuscripts, Ms. Nos. — 5, 6, 9, 11, 57 (A), 62, 64, 66, 77, 81, 82, 83, 94, 96, 97 and 99; Assamese Manuscripts, Ms. Nos. — 5, 6, 7, 13, 17 and 19 (— Shashi Bhushan Das Gupta, *op. cit.*). Sanskrit Manuscripts — Ms. Nos. 2-7A (eight texts bound together in colourfully painted wooden *patas*) and Ms. No. 91 (with illustrated folios) [— *A Descriptive Catalogue of Sanskrit Manuscripts*

Preserved In The North Bengal State Library of Cooch Behar, Published by: North Bengal State Library, Cooch Behar, Printed by: Umanath Printing Works, New Town-Guriahati (Chitrakar Para Road), Cooch Behar: 736 101, 2010]. Thus, there are 16 (sixteen) Bengali, 6 (six) Assamese and 2 (two), i.e., 24 (twenty four) illustrated manuscripts at the Library.

Manuscripts preserved at the Cooch Behar Sahitya Sabha, — Sanskrit Manuscripts, Ms. No. XLVII. Proably, there are more, which had not been recorded on the Catalogue. Dileep Kanjilal observed that the decoration on the wooden covers of the Mss. exhibited kings and monks dressed in ‘Sino-Tibetan’ style [— Dileep Kumar Kanjilal (Ed.), *A Descriptive Catalogue Of The Sanskrit Manuscripts Preserved in the Sahitya Sabha of Cooch Behar*, Published by: Baidyanath Chakravorty, Secretary, Sahitya Sabha, Cooch Behar, Printed by: Bimal Bhadury, B.B. Co. 4, Ram Ratan Bose Lane, Calcutta-700 004, 1978, Introduction, p. 15 and p. 46].

^x Sarat Chandra Ghoshal, *A History Of Cooch Behar*, *op. cit.*, Bibliography, pp. 5-6.

Shashi Bhushan Das Gupta’s Catalogue of Bengali Manuscripts ends with Ms. No. 102. There is no mention of the *Harabhakti-Taranga* in his Catalogue. Swapan Kumar Ray, mentions the manuscript having the serial no. 109 (1) in the Catalogue (new?) of Bengali Manuscripts preserved at the North Bengal State Library Archive (— Swapan Kumar Ray, *op. cit.*, p. 288). The portrait of Maharaja Shivendra Narayan mentioned by Ahmed, which was preserved at the State Library is probably the same mentioned by Sarat Chandra Ghoshal (1939 C.E.), which had influence of Mughal art and was preserved at the Lansdowne Hall, [— Sarat Chandra Ghoshal (Ed.), *Maharaj Shivendranarayaner Sangeet Sangraha*, Published by: Khan Chowdhuri Amanatulla Ahmed from Cooch Behar Sahitya Sabha, Printed at the Beena Press, Cooch Behar, 1345 B.S., Introduction, p. 8] where on its first floor along with the Public Hall the State Library was housed till 1969 C.E.

^{xi} Nirupama Devi (Ed.), *Paricharika (Naba Paryaya)*, 2nd Year, 1st Issue, Printed from: Cooch Behar State Press by Manmatha Nath Chattopadhyaya, Published by: Cooch Behar Sahitya Sabha, Agrahayana, 1324 B.S., p. 1.

^{xii} Sarat Chandra Ghoshal (Ed.), *Maharaj Harendranarayaner Granthavali, Prathama Khanda, Geetavali*, Published by: Khan Chowdhuri Amanatulla Ahmed from Cooch Behar Sahitya Sabha, 1327 B.S.

^{xiii} According to Dr. Nripendra Nath Pal, on the first half of c.1980s, the images of Maharajas Harendra and Shivendra Narayan adorned the north-wall of a room located on the south-west of the southern veranda at the ground-floor of Lansdowne Hall. The room at that time housed the Additional District Magistrate’s Chamber. But, these black and white images were photographs made from paintings and were not the original paintings themselves. On the said period Pal engaged the ‘Photographic Emporium’ to take photographs of the images. The two photographs captured from the images were subsequently published by Pal in his edited work *Maharaja Harendra Narayan O Shibendra Narayaner Bhakti Geeti Sangraha* [— Dr. Nripendra Nath Pal (Ed.), *Maharaja Harendra Narayan O Shibendra Narayaner Bhakti Geeti Sangraha*, Published by: Dwijadas Kar, Anima Prakashani, 141, Keshab Chandra Sen Street, Calcutta - 700 009, 2nd September, 1999, p. 55 (b)]. It was on c.2012-2014, when Pal had seen the original photographs for the last time which were kept on the floor of the Club room on the rear-side of the ground-floor of the Hall, since the office was being painted then. [— Dr. Nripendra Nath Pal, eminent Researcher and Writer on Cooch Behar History, Interviewed by the author on 1st June, 2021.] Presently the whereabouts of the original paintings and the photographs are not known.

^{xiv} According to the information provided by Christie's London (<https://onlineonly.christies.com>), the seated portrait of the Dewan is of Bengal School, circa 1840. It has opaque pigments heightened with gold on paper, holding a hookah pipe in his left hand. The identification inscription in black (white?) Devanagari script above — 'Ram Chandra Lahiri Cooch Behar Ka Wazir', within polychrome floral margins and wide yellow border, mounted. The painting is 7½ x 5¼ in. (17.9 x 13.1 cm.); the folio 9½ x 6⅞ in. (23.2 x 17.5 cm.). It was sold for GBP 2,000 (presently ₹ 1, 99,875.85), from Christie's, London, on the 7th of April, 2011 (lot 284).

Radha Krishna Lahiri and his eldest son Kali Chandra Lahiri, both at a time served as Dewans of Cooch Behar and were the father and brother of Ram Chandra Lahiri respectively. They were originally the inhabitants of Nal Danga, Rangpur, where the Lahiri family held a Zamindari. (— Mahimchandra Majumdar, *Gaurde Brahman*, Calcutta: Printed and published by: B.L. Chakravarti, New School-Book Press, 8, Dixon's Lane, 1886, pp. 123-125; Rev. R. Robinson, *op. cit.*, Chapter XVII, p. 203 and p. 205) Therefore, the painting can also bear a connection with Rangpur.

^{xv} Rev. R. Robinson, *op. cit.*, Chapter XVII, p. 205 and Chapter XXVIII, pp. 232-233.

^{xvi} Martin Montgomery, *The History, Antiquities, Topography, And Statistics Of Eastern India &c. &c.*, Vol. III, Puraniya, Ronggopoor, And Assam, London: W. H. Allen And Co., Leadenhall-Street, Printed By W. Nicol, 51, Pall-Mall, MDCCCXXXVIII (1838 C.E.), p. 434, Pl. II.

^{xvii} *Ibid.*, pp. 441, Pl. III, p. 450, Pl. IV, p. 451 (figure), p. 452 and p. 592, Pl. VI.

^{xviii} *The Illustrated London News*, Vol. XLVI, Jan.-June, 1865, Printed And Published By George C. Leighton, 198, Strand, London, — No. 1299, Saturday, January 28, p. 88; No. 1300, Saturday, February 4, p. 121; Nos. 1312-1313, Saturday, April 29, p. 409; No. 1314, Saturday, May 6, p. 440 and No. 1321, Saturday, June 24, pp. 600, 615.

^{xix} Jacob Bronowski, Sir Barry Gerald, James Fisher and Sir Julian Huxley (Editors), Introduction ('Technology for Mankind'), *Technology—Man Remakes His World*, 1963.

^{xx} Simon Ringsmuth, *The dPS Ultimate Guide to Photography Terms, A Glossary of Common Words and Phrases*, Publisher: Darren Rowse, www.digital-photography-school.com, 2017, p. 12.

^{xxi} Harendra Narayan Chaudhuri, *The Cooch Behar State And Its Land Revenue Settlements, (With An Introduction By Rai Bahadur Calica Doss Dutt, C.I.E.)*, Published under authority, Cooch Behar: Printed At The Cooch Behar State Press, 1903, p. 282.

^{xxii} Shashi Bhushan Haldar, 'Kochbeharadhipati Maharaj Narendranarayan Bhup Bahadurer Jivancharita', (Seventh Lecture), *Cooch Behar Hitaishini Sabha Bakritamala*, (Ed. Shashi Bhushan Haldar), 1865 C.E., Republished and Edited by Dr. Nripendra Nath Pal, Published by: Dwijadas Kar, Anima Prakashani, 141, Keshab Chandra Sen Street, Kolkata - 700 009, 12th January, 2004, p. 113.

^{xxiii} Harendra Narayan Chaudhuri, *op. cit.*, p. 283.

^{xxiv} Ghosh, Siddhartha, *Chabi Tola: Bangalir Photographi-Charcha*, Ananda Publishers Private Limited, 45, Beniatola Lane, Calcutta — 700 009, First Edition, January, 1988, Second Re-print, April 2015, pp. 31, 33, 36 and pp. 42-47.

^{xxv} *Ibid.*, pp. 32-33.

^{xxvi} *Ibid.*, pp. 31 and 41.

^{xxvii} *Ibid.*, pp. 41-42, and p. 47.

^{xxviii} *Ibid.*, pp. 41-42, end note no. 14 (p. 222) and p. 50.

^{xxix} Alok Ray, *Rajendralal Mitra*, Published by: Prashanta Kumar Palit, Bagartha, 1/3 Krishnaram Bosu Street, Kalikata-4, Printed by: S. Roy, Bidyut Printing Press, 17, Bheem Ghosh Lane, Kalikata-6, 1969, p. 56.

^{xxx} *Ibid.*, p. 36, p. 38, pp. 55-56.

^{xxxi} *Ibid.*, pp. 55-56 and end note no. 26 (pp. 98-99).

^{xxxii} *Bicentenary Souvenir, The Asiatic Society, 1784-1984*, Published by: Dr. Chandan Roy Chowdhury, General Secretary, The Asiatic Society, Calcutta and Printed at Lalchand Roy & Co. Private Limited, 7 & 7/1, Grant Lane, Calcutta-700 012, Presidents And General Secretaries Of The Asiatic Society, 1884-1983 (List).

^{xxxiii} Shashi Bhushan Haldar, *op. cit.*, p. 114.

‘Agricultural Society’ is most probably — ‘The Agricultural And Horticultural Society Of India’, established on 2nd October, 1820 C.E., now known as — ‘The Agri-Horticultural Society Of India’, Kolkata. Rev. William Carey, who was admitted a Member of the Asiatic Society on 1806 C.E., served as the first Secretary of The Agricultural And Horticultural Society Of India.

^{xxxiv} Shashi Bhushan Haldar, *op. cit.*, p. 115.

^{xxxv} *Ibid.*, p. 113.

^{xxxvi} Ananda Chandra Ghosh, ‘Kochbeharer Itihas, (Eighth Lecture)’, *Cooch Behar Hitaishini Sabha Baktritamala*, *op. cit.*, p. 149.

^{xxxvii} Deen Doyal Chaudhuri, *Nripendra-Smriti Or A Short Sketch &c. &c.*, Published by: Durgadoyal Chaudhuri, Bengal Book Club, 14, Ram Mohan Datta Road, Bhawanipur, Kolikata, Kolikata: Printed by: Mahesh Chandra Bhattacharyya, from Bharatmihir Yantra, 25 Ray Bagan Street, 1915, p. 8.

^{xxxviii} *Harabhakti-Taranga* [Ms. no. 109 (1)], *vide supra*, end note no. 10.

^{xxxix} Harendra Narayan Chaudhuri, *op. cit.*, p. 287.

^{xl} Siddharta Ghose, *op. cit.*, pp. 31-32.

^{xli} *Ibid.*, p. 43.

^{xlii} *Ibid.*, p. 42.

^{xliii} Willfried Baatz, *Photography: An Illustrated Historical Overview*, New York: Barron's, ISBN 0-7641-0243-5, 1997, p. 17.

^{xliv} Robert Hunt, *Manual Of Photography*, Fourth Edition, Revised, London And Glasgow: Richard Griffin And Company, Publishers To The University Of Glasgow, Glasgow: W.G. Blackie And Co., Printers, Villafield, 1854, p. 12.

^{xlv} Willfried Baatz, *op. cit.*, p. 16.

^{xlvi} Ray Desmond, 'Photography In Victorian India', *Journal of the Royal Society of Arts*, Vol. 134, No. 5353, Published by: Royal Society for the Encouragement of Arts, Manufacturers and Commerce, December, 1985, p. 49.

^{xlvii} *Ibid.*, pp. 49 & 51.

^{xlviii} Alex Strasser, *Victorian Photography: Being an Album of Yesterday's Camera-Work*, London and New York, Printed in Great Britain for the Focal Press Ltd., 31, Fitzroy Square, London, W.I. at The Windmill Press, Kingswood, Surrey, First printed: November, 1942, pp. 36-37.

^{xlix} Ray Desmond, *op. cit.*, pp. 49 & 51.

¹ *Ibid.*, p. 51.

[For a detailed history of origin of the concept of photography see — Geoffrey Batchen, *Burning With Desire: The Conception Of Photography*, Massachusetts Institute Of Technology, United States Of America, ISBN 0-262-52259-4 (pb), 1997, First MIT Press paperback edition, 1999, pp. 24-50.]

^{li} *Ibid.*, p. 49.

^{lii} Siddharta Ghose, *op. cit.*, p. 19.

^{liii} 'Colonel Haughton was deputed by Government (as Commissioner) to Cooch Behar in consequence of the setting up of a fraudulent will and of dissension among the family. Such a step was "considered by Government to be imperatively called for, as the only means of effectually providing for the care and education of the young Raja, for the security of the Government revenue (tribute), and for the defence of the Bhutan Frontier, for which the Government was responsible."' [— A. Claude Campbell, *Glimpses Of Bengal (A Comprehensive, Archaeological, Biographical, and Pictorial History of Bengal, Behar and Orissa)*, Vol. I, Published by: Campbell & Medland, 3 and 4, Hare Street, Calcutta; Printed by: S. Clarke, Photochromic And General Book Printer, 41, Granby Row, Manchester, Eng., 1907, p. 42].

Also see — Harendra Narayan Chaudhuri, *op. cit.*, (*passim*), p. 287 and fn. no. 117, pp. 326-327, p. 424, pp. 426-430 (Lieutenant-Governor Sir Rivers Thompson's Speech) and p. 430 (His Highness' Reply).

^{liv} W.O.A. Beckett, *Completion Settlement Report Of Pergunnah Mekhligunge In The Cooch Behar State*, Cooch Behar State Press, October 7, 1874, p. II, para 35, NBSLA.

^{lv} Though the surname ‘Govan’ can be found outside of Europe, but it is of Scottish origin. It is a habitational name from Govan near Glasgow, Scotland [— Patrick Hanks (Ed.), *Dictionary of American Family Names*, Volume Two, G-N, Published by: Oxford University Press, Inc., 198, Madison Avenue, New York, 10016, 1st Edition, Print ISBN-13: 9780195165586, March 1, 2003, p. 71].

^{lvi} *The Illustrated London News*, Vol. XLVIII, (Jan.-June, 1866), Printed And Published By George C. Leighton, 198, Strand, London, No. 1361, Saturday, March 17, 1866, p. 276.

^{lvii} *Loc. cit.*

^{lviii} Rev. R. Robinson, *op. cit.*, Chapter VIII, pp. 156-157.

The English translation of the *Rajopakhyan* by Rev. R. Robinson does not assure that the palace was built, it states that the European architect — ‘...drew a plan of a splendid three-storied house which was to be furnished with mirrors, chandeliers, and other furniture necessary for purposes of entertainment. (pp. 156-157)’ However, the two *Rajopakhyan* manuscripts preserved with the present author [— Moonshi Joynath Ghose, *Rajopakhyan*, Pratyaksha Khanda, Ashtam-Adhyaya, folio 41-B and p. 22 (of Note Book No. 2; this Ms. has been copied in two Note-books, it is an incomplete Manuscript) of Ms. Nos. 1 and 2 respectively] and Biswanath Das, [— Biswanath Das (Ed.), *Satik Rajopakhyan (History of Cooch Behar)*, Published by: Jayanta Shee, The Shee Book Agency, 210A, Mukhtaram Babu Street, Kolkata: 700 007, ISBN 978-81-924625-9-2, First Published: January, 2014, Pratyaksha Khanda, Ashtam-Adhyaya, p. 200] following Mushi Joynath Ghosh’s language caterers the information in a positive assertion, but, in contrary to the first Ms. and Robinson’s translation, the later Ms. (No. 2) and Das’s work does not mention of any ‘three-storied’ house. Whatever so, the inflection (‘to be’) in Rev. R. Robinson’s translation cannot simply be put aside.

Later on, while translating the events which occurred in-between *Agrahayan* (November-December), 291 to 292 *Rajshaka* corresponding with 1207-1208 B.S. and 1800-1802 C.E. Robinson mentioned about a ‘three-storied dullan’ in which the Maharaja after having his breakfast sometimes used to sit where amusement was provided (Chapter XIII, p. 186). The aforementioned Manuscript No. 1 (— Moonshi Joynath Ghose, *op. cit.*, Pratyaksha Khanda, Trayodash-Adhyaya folio 48-A of Ms. 1) and Das’s Edition (— Biswanath Das, *op. cit.*, Pratyaksha Khanda, Trayodash-Adhyaya, p. 217) agrees with this information. It is quite possible that these two three-storied buildings were the same. But, considering the imprecision of Robinson’s translation further extrapolation beyond conjecture would be at stake. Ahmed, regarding Robinson’s translation commented in his work — ‘In the title page of the translated work the name of the writer has been mentioned as ‘Jadunath Ghose’. There are also many mistakes like this in the translation which cannot be overlooked. Some works have been written on the basis of this translation. The writers of some of these works have only increased the number of such mistakes in their attempt to express in their own language this incorrect translation.’ (— Sarat Chandra Ghoshal, *A History Of Cooch Behar, op. cit.*, Bibliography, p. 4).

^{lix} *Ibid.*, Chapter XVIII, pp. 206-207.

This information receives further support from the Report of Captain Thomas Herbert Lewin. As late as in 1876 C.E., Lewin wrote — ‘The palace is a brick building, dating from the year 1828 A.D., built by Harendra Narayan, the seventeenth (should be sixteenth) Raja.’ (Quoted in — W.W. Hunter, *A Statistical Account Of Bengal*, Vol. X, Districts Of Darjiling And Jalpaiguri, And State Of Kuch Behar, Trubner & Co., London, Murray And Gibb Edinburgh,

Printers To Her Majesty's Stationary Office, 1876, p. 360). Campbell reproduced the same year and class of information in brief in his work. (— A. Claude Campbell, *op. cit.*, p. 308).

^{lx} *Ibid.*, Chapter XXVII, p. 230.

^{lxi} Shashi Bhushan Haldar, *op. cit.*, p. 126.

^{lxii} Harendra Narayan Chaudhuri, *op. cit.*, p. 330.

^{lxiii} Tribhanga Mukhopadhyaya, 'Vidya Vishayak (First Lecture)', *Cooch Behar Hitaishini Sabha Bakritamala*, *op. cit.*, p. 35.

^{lxiv} Harendra Narayan Chaudhuri, *op. cit.*, p. 330.

^{lxv} Binoy Sen, 'Cooch Behar Shaharer Gorapattan: Pourashabhar Janma', *Cooch Behar Jela Pradarshanir Mukhapatra Smaranika, 1971*, Edited by: Smaranika Upa-Samiti, Printed from: (Cooch Behar —) United Printers, Beena Press, Cooch Behar Press, Kohinoor Printing Works, Sulekha Press, Kamala Printing Works, Swadeshi Art Press and Jayanti Press, Published by: Jela Pradarshanir Smaranika Upa-Samiti, Published on: Republic Day, 1971, p. 92.

^{lxvi} *Ibid.*

^{lxvii} Harendra Narayan Chaudhuri, *op. cit.*

^{lxviii} *Ibid.*, p. 332.

^{lxix} Quoted in — W.W. Hunter, *op. cit.*, p. 360.

Sabitri Devi, the second daughter of the renowned Brahma Preacher Brahmananda Keshav Chandra Sen and Jaganmohini Devi, was married to Kumar Gajendra Narayan Senior, a cousin of Maharaja Nripendra Narayan on the 13th August, 1881 C.E. Sabitri Devi first came to Cooch Behar on 1884 C.E.. She recalls in her book that the palace was of thatched grass, there was a room or structure within the palace only which was merely *pucca*. (— Sabitri Devi, *Swargiya Kumar Gajendra Narayan*, Calcutta: Lakshmi Bilas Press, 1928, pp. 13, 17-18 and 23). This appears to be her memory of the thatched house or houses only, which was or were '*the real dwelling-place of the family (Thomas Herbert Lewin, 1876 C.E.)*'. This cannot be accepted for the entire palace buildings.

^{lxx} Rev. R. Robinson, *op. cit.*, Chapter XVIII, p. 207.

^{lxxi} *Loc. cit.*

^{lxxii} Ananda Chandra Ghosh, *op. cit.*, pp. 135-136.

Ananda Chandra Ghosh does not specify the number of brick buildings in the palace, but records of their inelegant and incongruous existence. Almost after two decades, Bhagavati Charan Banerjee, mentions the old palace to be unembellished. He does not specify the number of brick built edifices either, but puts the number to be two or three and all of the remaining to be of thatched grass (— Bhagavati Charan Banerjee, *History Of Cooch Behar*, 2nd Edition, Cooch Behar: Printed At The Cooch Behar State Press, 1884, p. 39).

^{lxxiii} Biswanath Das, *op. cit.*, p. 352.

Whatever the conditions of the buildings were, the map bears testimony that the palace campus was undoubtedly large. Maharani Sunity Devi recalls in her memoir — ‘When I first came to Cooch Behar (c.1878-1882) we lived in the old palace, which was like a town. Hundreds of ladies occupied the various houses of which it was composed: the late Maharajah’s (Maharaja Narendra Narayan) wives, his mother and grandmother, and many relations, with all their servants. Whenever there were festivities all these ladies gathered together and it was like a great crowd in a small city.’ (— Sunity Devee, *The Autobiography Of An Indian Princess*, London: John Murray, Albemarle Street, W., Printed By William Clowes And Sons, Limited, London And Beccles, England, 1921, p. 92).

It is quite conceivable that the name ‘Tarabari’ derived from Goddess *Jay Tara*. The metal image of *Shree Shree Jay Tara* was established by Maharaja Harendra Narayan towards the close of 289 *Rajshaka*, corresponding with 1205 B.S and 1799 C.E. (— Rev. R. Robinson, *op. cit.*, Chapter X, pp. 168-169).

^{lxxiv} Moonshi Joynath Ghose mentioned that Maharaja Shivendra Narayan demolished all of the *kucha* temples in front of the palace and erected *pucca* structures in their stead. This was probably done some time in between c.1842-1843 (corresponding with 333 *Rajashaka* or 1249 B.S.) as can be assessed from his description. (— Rev. R. Robinson, *op. cit.*, Chapter XXX, p. 238). Ms. No. 1 of *Rajopakhyan* (— Moonshi Joynath Ghose, *op. cit.*, Pratyaksha Khanda, Trinshat-Adhyaya, folio 61-B) makes use of the terms ‘*kuccha-ghar*’ (earthen-room) and ‘*uttama uttama prasada*’ (palatial buildings, i.e., brick-built structures) and in the edition by Biswanath Das (— Biswanath Das, *op. cit.*, Pratyaksha Khanda, Trinshat-Adhyaya, p. 251), in lieu of the terms ‘*kucha*’ and ‘*pucca*’, the words ‘earthen’ and ‘brick-built’ has been used respectively, which indicates that all of the temples or their adjacent structures were not necessarily completely brick structures but, could have been semi-pucca as the one on the right hand side of the photograph as well.

^{lxxv} Ashruman Das Gupta, (24th February, 1894 C.E.-22nd September, 1975 C.E.), a distinguished Tutor of the Cooch Behar Royal family, almost over a sesquicentenary later wrote (c.1970s), till 1888 C.E., as long as the Madan Mohan Temple was located to the northern side of the main gate of Cooch Behar palace, the *Ras Mela* was held therein. Afterwards, the *Mela* shifted when the temple was removed to its present ground [— Ashruman Das Gupta, ‘Cooch Behar Rasmelar Sankshipta Itihas’, *Rasmela 1973 (Souveneir)*, Published by: Cooch Behar Municipality, Printed from: Parijat Press, Cooch Behar, 1973].

^{lxxvi} It is interesting to note that as a result of the Second Bhutan War which commenced on November, 1864 C.E. the Treaty of Sitchula was signed with British India and Bhutan on the 11th of November, 1865 C.E. [— Nagendra Singh, *Bhutan: A Kingdom In The Himalayas: A Study of the Land, its People and their Government*, 2nd Edition, Thomson Press (India) Limited Publication Division, New Delhi, 1978, Appendix VII – The Treaty of Sinchula, p. 243].

^{lxxvii} *Vide supra* end note nos. 58 and 71.

‘To the west is a flower garden formerly attached to the old palace, and in days gone by a favourite resort of the Maharaja’s (Nripendra Narayan) grandfather (and great grandfather?). It is neatly laid out and well kept; it was at one time surrounded by a high wall, but it suffered much during the great earthquake and has not been restored. ...In the south-west corner of the park are the stables [‘place for his (the Maharaja’s) horses’ (Moonshi Joynath Ghose, 1230-1240 B.S. – 1252 B.S.)!], which are well-planned and well-built buildings with a façade to the east surmounted

by a clock-tower [‘Gharikhana’ (Moonshi Joynath Ghose, 1230-1240 B.S. – 1252 B.S.)?].’ (— A. Claude Campbell, *op. cit.*, p. 313).

It becomes persuasive to assign the three structures, despite of the conceived ‘pleasure-house’ on the right hand side of the photograph to be new, but without any substantial proof it would be all empty blustering. It is also of certain curiosity, that when the drawing parlours and even the stables (latter modified) were *pucca* why the Maharaja use to reside in a mat hut? Though, this is not our subject of discussion, but just for information, in an earthquake prone area like Cooch Behar, mat huts were (/are) more secure and also healthy if maintained regularly.

lxxviii Harendra Narayan Chaudhuri, *op. cit.*, p. 332.

lxxix Alex Strasser, *op. cit.*, pp. 50, 53.

lxxx Harendra Narayan Chaudhuri, *op. cit.*, pp. 419-420.

lxxxi Deen Doyal Chaudhuri, *op. cit.*, p. 30 and pp. 27, 37, 44.

Image on the p. 27 of this book is captioned as ‘Shaishabe’ or Maharaja in his early childhood on the list of illustrations, but, as ‘Balya Bayase’ or as a young boy on the caption, while that on p. 30 (the earliest known image of the Maharaja mentioned above, supposed to be taken in-between c.1872-1874) bears the caption, the Maharaja as a young boy (‘Balak’), but, comparing both the images surely leads to the conclusion that the image on p. 30 precedes the another on p. 27.

lxxxii *Ibid.*, p. 50.

The assumption of the image on the postcard, that it was taken on or around the year c.1878, i.e., the year of the Maharaja's marriage with Maharani Sunity Devi, has been made on the basis of the caption on the list of illustrations mentioned above, which in English follows as — ‘*Maharajah Nripendra Narayan (marriage-time)*’. If the postcard image and the image on p. 50 cited above were taken on the same time then, both of them share a connection with the period of Maharaja's marriage.

lxxxiii *Cooch Behar Raj Sarkarer Sahit Gobrachhara Mustofi Bangsher Sambandhe Sankshipta Bibaran*, Beena Printing Works Ltd., Jalpaiguri, (~ c.1925), pp. 2-3 and Unpublished Annexure (hand-written).

lxxxiv Shreesh Chandra Mustofi, Kolkata, (born on: 12th October, 1935, Cooch Behar, died on: 3rd August, 2020, Kolkata), it seems that the particular date is missing, this citation forms a part of a series of Interview taken (mostly by audio-recording) by the author from 2015-2020.

The door-like structure seen on the left hand-side of the photograph when compared to the doors from available images of the main house at Gobrachhara shows no semblance.

lxxxv Gyanendranath Kumar, *Bangsha-Parichaya*, Vol.-VIII, Published by: Prajapati-Sampadak Gyanendranath Kumar, 209, Cornwallis Street, Kolikata (Kolkata), Printed by: P.K. Pal, New Aryya Mission Press, 9, Sibnarayan Dass Lane, Calcutta, Paush, 1335 B.S. (c.1928-1929), p. 122.

^{lxxxvi} Sitangsu Sekhar Mustafi, (born on: 6th July, 1945, Dinhata), Dinhata, Interviewed by the author on 30th March, 2021 via Audio-recording.

^{lxxxvii} Siddhartha Ghosh, *op. cit.*, p. 6.

^{lxxxviii} Nripendra Narayan, *Thirty-Seven Years Of Big Game Shooting In Cooch Behar, The Duars, And Assam, (A Rough Diary By The Maharajah Of Cooch Behar)*, London: Rowland Ward, Limited, 167, Piccadilly; Bombay: Bennett, Coleman & Co., The Times Press, 1908, pp. 30-33.

^{lxxxix} *Ibid.*, pp. 47-48, 49-50 and pp. 66-68.

The caption on p. 50 of the book reads as 'Skinning the 9'-9" Tiger shot on 22nd Feb. 1885', the year mentioned appears to be a printing mistake, it should be 1887 C.E. The reference to this shoot is given on p. 49 of the same.

^{xc} Lord Frederic Hamilton, *My Yesterdays: Here, There And Everywhere*, Vol. III, Eighteenth Edition, Hodder And Stoughton Limited, London, Made and Printed in Great Britain, Butler & Tanner Ltd., Frome and London, p. 21.

^{xci} Nripendra Narayan, *op. cit.*, pp. 94-96.

^{xcii} *Ibid.*, pp. 163-166.

^{xciii} *Ibid.*, pp. 277-278, also see — pp. 231, 243, 258 and p. 282.

^{xciv} The book contains 153 (one hundred and fifty three) images in total.

^{xcv} *Annual Administration Report Of The Cooch Behar State For The Year 1885-86*, Cooch Behar: Printed At The Cooch Behar State Press, 1887, 3. Revenue Administration (Report of the Revenue Department), From Babu Calica Doss Dutt, Dewan of Cooch Behar, To His Highness The Maharajah Bhup Bahadur In Council, Cooch Behar. Dated, Cooch Behar, September, 1886, Section I.-Land Revenue, pp. 12-13, para 57, NBSLA.

^{xcvi} Siddhartha Ghosh, *op. cit.*, pp. 149-150.

^{xcvii} *Ibid.*, p. 152.

According to Shree Sujit Ghose, Indraprastha, Baharampur, grandson of Late Ambika Charan Roy, Interviewed by the author on the 13th of August, 2020 via audio-recording, most of the photographs (and/or their negatives) taken by late Ambika Charan Roy are now lost with time.

Illustration

Fig.-1: Above: a hunting scene featuring *Anangamohan*, the prince of Kalinga and his friend *Anandabihari*, the minister's son; below: the prince *Anangamohan* and his newly married bride *Swapnabati* riding together on the same horse, *Anandabihari* is seen riding in front of them, [Source: Sarat Chandra Ghoshal (Ed.), *Maharaj Harendranarayaner Granthavali, Chaturtha Khanda, Upakatha*, 1336 B.S., p. 32].

Fig.-2: A portrait of Maharaja Harendra Narayan (1783-1839 C.E.) of Cooch Behar, [Source: Sarat Chandra Ghoshal (Ed.), *Maharaj Harendranarayaner Granthavali, Prathama Khanda, Geetavali*, 1327 B.S.].

Fig.-3: One of the portraits of Nawab Wajid Ali Shah (1822-1887 C.E.) of Awadh for comparison. The miniature painting of Ram Chandra Lahiri, Dewan of Cooch Behar State (c.1826/27-1840), is available at the Christie's Website (<https://onlineonly.christies.com>).

PALACE OF THE RAJAH, COOCH BEHAR.

THE territory of Cooch Behar, which is situated to the north of Bengal, adjoining Ebootan, is ruled by a Hindoo Prince or Rajah, who is a vassal of the British Government and is obliged to pay the half of his yearly revenue into the treasury at Calcutta. The capital of this small tributary State is a town of the same name on the River

Toreaha, 350 miles from Calcutta. The present Rajah, who has been educated in one of the colleges maintained by the Government of Bengal, has acquired, like many other natives of the highest rank in India, a considerable share of European knowledge and mental culture. The view of his newly-built palace which we have engraved is from

a photograph by Dr. G. M. Govan. At the time it was taken the edifice was scarcely finished, and its aspect was marred in some degree by the unsightly structures, of a temporary character, which still remained beside it, as well as by the roughness of the ground in front.

Fig.-4: The first known photograph of Cooch Behar featuring the old Cooch Behar Palace and the Rasa-Chakra, [Source: *The Illustrated London News*, Vol. XLVIII, March 17, 1866, p. 276].

Fig.-5: An undated map of Cooch Behar Town from Maharaja Narendra Narayan's time (1847-1863 C.E.), showing the relative position of the palace compound and palace buildings; [Source: Biswanath Das (Ed.), *Satik Rajopakhyan*, January, 2014, p. 352].

Fig.6: The *Rasa-Chakra* of Cooch Behar for comparison, 9th November, 2014, [Image: Author].

Fig.-7: The earliest known photograph of Maharaja Nripendra Narayan (1863-1911 C.E.). Here the young Maharaja (centre) is seen with his cousins, namely Kumar Gajendra Narayan Senior (left) and Junior (right) and their Tutor and Guardian Mr. H. St. John Kneller, c.1872-1874, [Source: Deen Doyal Chaudhuri, *Nripendra-Smriti*, 1915, p. 30].

Fig.-8: Left: A printed post card of young Maharaja Nripendra Narayan (c.1878) by Bourne & Shepherd. Right: Maharaja Nripendra Narayan, at the time of his marriage (c.1878) (Bourne & Shepherd?), [Source: Deen Doyal Chaudhuri, *Nripendra-Smriti*, 1915, p. 50]. Besides other similarities, note the similarity of the hat on the right hand-side of the Maharaja in both of the images.

Fig.-9: The portrait of Baikuntha Chandra Mustofi (c.1840s-13th June, 1877 C.E.), premier Zamindar of Cooch Behar State, c.1877; it is the first known photograph from Cooch Behar taken outside the Royal arena, [Courtesy: Late Shreesh Chandra Mustofi, Kolkata].

Fig.-10: The first Tiger shot of 1885 C.E. at the Falimari Jungles, Tufanganj, Cooch Behar, [Source: Nripendra Narayan, *Thirty-Seven Years Of Big Game Shooting*, 1908, p. 31].

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Fig.-11: A Shooting Camp at Garad Hat, Tufanganj, 1892 C.E., [Source: Nripendra Narayan, *Thirty-Seven Years Of Big Game Shooting*, 1908, p. 90].

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